

GINAMO workshop on genetic diversity indicators in Sweden

Stockholm, 26 March 2025

REPORT

This research was funded by Biodiversa+, the European Biodiversity Partnership, in the context of the GINAMO project under the 2022-2023 BiodivMon joint call. It was co-funded by the European Commission (GA No. 101052342) The Research Council of Norway, The Belgian Science Policy, L'Agence nationale de la recherche, Ministero dell'Università, Naturvårdsverket, Rymdstyrelsen, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft and Innovation Fund Denmark

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Suggested citation: Vejlggaard, C. R., Leus, K., Andersson, A., Köppä, V., Laikre, L., Lundmark, C., & Hvilson, C. (2025). *GINAMO workshop on genetic diversity indicators in Sweden* (Project report). GINAMO: Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring. DOI: <https://zenodo.org/records/17017810>

GINAMO Genetic Indicators for Nature Monitoring

Genetic diversity is the foundation of biodiversity and essential for the long-term survival, adaptation, and resilience of populations, species, and entire ecosystems. While genetic diversity has long been neglected in biodiversity policy and management, the current Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD)

Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF) includes a strong goal and target for genetic diversity conservation and also monitoring, including with indicators and for wild species. Tools and indicators to assess and monitor genetic diversity are available but are rarely applied due to the gap in knowledge transfer between conservation science and application. GINAMO is a project of Biodiversa+, The European Biodiversity Partnership, which assesses and delivers science-based and co-designed best practices and guidelines for the use of genetic diversity indicators. This will enable the routine integration of genetic criteria and indicators into biodiversity monitoring and assessments, from policy at regional, national, and EU levels, to global conventions and obligations. A key component of GINAMO is the use of facilitated group decision-making processes to partner and co-decide from the outset with the stakeholder community. This ensures that all resources produced meet their concerns, reporting duties, and monitoring needs, and that guidelines and work flows are more likely to be adopted. Easy-to-apply, standardised and automated workflows will be co-created for assessing genetic indicators to meet national reporting obligations and to incorporate genetic diversity knowledge into nature management plans.

Main objectives

GINAMO uses existing open access genetic and non-genetic data (including Earth observation data) to best determine accurate estimates of the two genetic diversity indicators of the GBF: 1) the proportion of populations within species with an effective population size (N_e) greater than 500 ($N_e > 500$ hereafter), and 2) the proportion of populations maintained within species. To maximise the implementation and reporting of these indicators, GINAMO designs, facilitates, and scientifically evaluates co-creation processes between scientists and country stakeholders in France, Italy, Belgium, Norway and Sweden. These processes aim to collaboratively develop workflows that are scientifically sound, appropriate, compliant with policy and easy-to-implement for nature management.

Main activities

GINAMO focuses on generating best practices for assessing effective population size and evaluating genetic indicators from both DNA-based data and non-DNA (proxy) data from multiple sources. Additionally, GINAMO evaluates how satellite Earth observation data can be used to generate proxies to monitor genetic diversity. Workflows for existing and newly generated information will be standardised to provide easily accessible tools for researchers, nature managers and policy makers. GINAMO activities follow a co-creation approach under professional guidance by the European Regional Resource Center of the IUCN SSC [Conservation Planning Specialist Group](#) and with scientific evaluation by social scientists, so that methods and products are produced together by policy makers, nature managers, and scientists.

Workshop process

The workshops organised by GINAMO in collaboration with local country stakeholders serve to create input to the best practice guidelines that will be produced. In order to make these as user friendly and as relevant as possible, it is important to understand the realities in which various stakeholders operate, and to understand the challenges they experience from their perspective. The challenges identified during the workshops will inform the work of the various work packages within GINAMO, when developing the science and methods behind the use of genetic indicators.

IUCN SSC CPSG Europe designed and facilitated the country workshop processes, in line with CPSG's Principles and Steps (Appendix II), and informed by preparatory meetings with a country organising group composed of GINAMO scientists from the country and selected country stakeholders with a central role in monitoring and reporting on biodiversity.

In preparation of the workshops, a generic workflow was developed (Fig 1), that outlines the main steps that need to be taken within a country in order to be able to report genetic indicators to the CBD. This workflow was used as the basis for the discussions during the workshop.

Fig 1. The generic workflow used as a base for the workshop.

The agenda for the workshop can be found in Appendix I. Following an introduction to the GINAMO project and the genetic indicators, as well as to the workshop process and generic workflow, the active part of the workshop started. Participants first identified where in the workflow they felt their institution could have a role to play. Next, the generic workflow was divided into three parts:

1. Selection of the species to monitor and report on.
2. Data collection, indicator calculation, and storing and structuring of metadata for future reporting cycles.

3. Preparing the relevant parts of the CBD report

For each of these three parts, the participants:

- A. Discussed their knowledge of the current situation in Sweden
- B. Identified the challenges facing them as stakeholders, or the country as a whole, in order to end up with a fully functional, and repeatable workflow that can routinely and consistently produce genetic indicators for consecutive reporting cycles to CBD.

At the end of the workshop, the participants reviewed all the challenges and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

Participants

The country organising group identified the stakeholders that would be invited to the workshop. A matrix was developed to help identify stakeholders that represented a wide variety of workflow steps, skills, roles and responsibilities, as well as geographical placement, when relevant. Not all the identified stakeholders were able to participate in the workshop, but they will all receive this report.

27 stakeholders representing various research institutes, nature monitoring agencies, environmental consultants and NGO's participated. The National Focal Point for the CBD attended the workshop as did some people who participated /negotiated in the COPS and other related CBD meetings. Workshop evaluation

Workshop evaluation

GINAMO's social scientists will evaluate the entire co-creation process. In order to evaluate the country workshops, a survey was prepared and completed by all participants before and after the workshop. The only parts from that survey included in this report are any answers to the question: "List any stakeholders who could have made a valuable contribution but were not present at this workshop". The overall results from this evaluation will be shared at a later stage.

Workshop results

Workshop outcomes

1. An overview of the current situation in Sweden with regards to: genetic monitoring and reporting, genetic and proxy data gathering and databases, already existing workflows, important stakeholder groups, scientific views regarding the use of the *Ne 500* headline indicator, etc.

2. A list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

3. A selection of those challenges for which developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country.

This report collects the results from the workshop in Sweden, and reflects the thoughts, assumptions and knowledge of the participants at the time of the workshop, but does not claim to give the full picture of the status and challenges with regards to the reporting of genetic indicators to the CBD in Sweden. The aim of this report is to inform further work by GINAMO and hopefully it will also prove to be a useful first step towards further work and collaboration within Sweden, to develop and implement a national workflow.

Where in the workflow stakeholders' institutions might contribute

The workshop participants identified where in the workflow they felt their institution might have a role to play. The results are in the table below. Please note that this does not constitute an exhaustive list of stakeholders required for each workflow step.

Data on species is generated Data about species is stored	Species list to monitor and report on	Data is collected, structured and stored	Indicators are calculated and stored	The report to the CBD is written and submitted
Centrum för biologisk mångfald (CBM) (SLU)	Naturvårdsverket (SEPA)	Stockholms universitet (SU)	Stockholms universitet (SU) (Zoology - genetic and proxy data; NATGEO, Earth Observation data)	Centrum för biologisk mångfald (CBM) (SLU)
Sveriges lantbruksuniversitet (SLU)	Skansen	Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (HaV)	Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (HaV)	Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (HaV)
Skansen	Nordens Ark	Uppsala universitet	Naturvårdsverket	Naturvårdsverket
Stockholms universitet (SU)	Stockholms universitet (SU)	Artsdatabanken (SLU)	Uppsala universitet	
Nordens Ark	Artdatabanken (SLU)	Naturhistoriska riksmuseet (NRM)*	Artsdatabanken (SLU)	

Göteborgs universitet (GU)	Sportfiskarna	Länsstyrelser (County Administrative Boards)*		
Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (HaV)	Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (HaV)	Statens veterinärmedicinska anstalt (SVA)*		
Artsdatabanken (SLU)	Calluna AB			
Ekologigruppen	Forestry*			
Calluna AB	Landowners*			
Göteborgs botaniska trädgård	Reindeer holders, Sami people*			
Uppsala universitet	Naturhistoriska riksmuseet (NRM)*			
Sportfiskarna	Svenska Jägareförbundet (Hunters association)*			
Naturhistoriska riksmuseet (NRM)*	Skogsstyrelsen*			
Länsstyrelser (County Administrative Boards)*	Regeringskansliet*			
Statens veterinärmedicinska anstalt (SVA)*				
Energy companies*				
NGO's were generally missing				

but could have important data*				
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*This organisation was identified as missing from the workshop or as one with a stake in the topic.

Summary of current situation in Sweden

One of the outcomes for the workshop was to create a common understanding of what the current situation concerning reporting to the CBD is. Therefore we asked a set of questions at the workshop to get an idea of how far Sweden has come with monitoring and calculating genetic indicators.

Naturvårdsverket (SEPA) has the formal responsibility from the government to do monitoring and reporting on all international legislations that Sweden is a signatory to and therefore it is SEPA who will be responsible for gathering the data and writing the next report which is due in February 2026.

The Swedish CBD focal points who will be involved in the reporting attended the workshop but the work of writing the report and deciding how the indicators would be reported on had not yet been started. SEPA should deliver the report to the government in November 2025.

SEPA has delegated the responsibility of monitoring marine and freshwater species to Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (HaV).

The two agencies do not do the monitoring work themselves but collaborate with several universities for the data collocation and indicator assessments.

Sweden has a national program for monitoring genetic diversity with DNA-data practically implemented since 2020. Currently ca 30 species are monitored from about 100 identified species and the selection of these has been based on needs for management purposes or political focus (such as harvested fish and pollinators). The list of species with DNA-based monitoring schemes expands as resources are available and the list is also adapted based on new or changing management needs. The national genetic indicators are more comprehensive than what is required from the CBD and are integrated in the monitoring schemes for SWAM and will also be so for SEPA.

Sweden participated in a recent study where over 900 species from 9 countries were assessed and the genetic indicators calculated based on available data (DNA as well as on-DNA data (proxy data); Masstretta-Yanes and da Silva et al 2024). The work for Sweden was conducted by Stockholm University in collaboration with Artdatabanken . For Sweden, genetic indicators were calculated for about 120 species. The assessed species were selected based on management interest (all amphibians and reptiles in the country were assessed), an evaluation of Action Plans as a source for indicator assessments (all APs reviewed), a selection of mammals to make possible a comparison with a previous, less detailed assessment ([Thurfjell et al. 2022](#)), and a wish to include several taxonomic groups. It is likely that these indicators will be part of the report to the CBD with some complementary analyses (Köppä et al., in press; Lyrholm, pers.com) .

A reality facing monitoring efforts in Sweden led by the agencies is that political budget decisions affect the work. These decisions are taken on an annual basis and long-term monitoring activities are therefore not secured.

SEPA is currently working to include monitoring of genetic diversity in the reporting of Article 17 of the Habitats Directive and while there may be an overlap of the people doing the various assessments outside of the agencies it is not the same departments within the agencies who work with the various reports.

Challenges

The workflow for reporting to CBD was divided into parts, and for each part, the workshop participants identified a list of challenges facing the stakeholders and the country to have a fully functional workflow that is repeatable for consecutive reporting cycles for the CBD.

After identifying the challenges, the participants reviewed them all and selected those for which they felt that developing solutions may benefit from collaboration with GINAMO (in other words, from co-creating solutions); versus those challenges that clearly need to be solved in-country. It was possible to mark a challenge as both a co-creation candidate and as a challenge that needs national work to be solved - but that is not indicated in this report. The challenges marked with (G) are the ones that were suggested for co-creation.

Data on species is generated

1. There are 22000 species in Artsdatabanken but not all of them have sufficient data for assessing the genetic indicators. Thurfjell et al. 2022 have analysed this in detail and shown e.g. that taxonomic groups vary in this respect.
2. There are some large data sources but there is also a lot of relevant data stored in personal computers held by individual researchers or managers that are difficult to access and may be lost when the person stops working.
3. A centralized long term biobank is needed: The Natural History Museum's biobank is full! There are biobanks but they are project financed and risk being eliminated once funding stops.
4. Environmental consultants collect a lot of data but there is a need to systemize and streamline the methodologies so that the data also can be used to calculate indicators and so that it is consistent over time.

Species list to monitor and report on

How to select species to monitor:

Sweden has over the years done several assessments and produced suggestions for how to select species for monitoring of genetic diversity (Laikre & Ryman 1997, Naturvårdsverket Rapport 4824; [Laikre et al 2008](#)). The latest assessments were done before the now run DNA-based monitoring and that report was used to select species for the SEPA monitoring (Posledovich et al 2021, Reports to 6958 and 6959 to SEPA). The species selected by SwAm was done by managers in the agency.

1. DNA monitoring

- The species we monitor genetically with DNA techniques have been selected by SwAM managers (12 species) and by SEPA managers following suggestions by Posledovich et al (2021a,b).
- The species currently monitored represents groups that are particularly relevant to monitor as outlined in Posledovich et al (2021a,b): heavy harvested species (moose, herring, cod), species subjected to large scale releases (salmon), habitat forming species (bladderwrack, eelgrass, feathermosses), non-disturbed, reference populations (brown trout), species subjected to restoration efforts (brown trout), pollinating species, species that are expected to be affected by climate change (bumblebees, Arctic charr),
- A priority has been given to species for which molecular data are already available, other monitoring is already ongoing so tissue samples can be easily collected, and/or time series tissue is available. This approach is cost effective.

2. Proxy monitoring (or a MIX not always clear from the discussion)

- We should work on “common” species, not just species under threat (as defined by the national red list). (G)
- Maybe Sweden should focus on species that are ecologically important, and phylogenetically important. (G)
- If one chooses species that are higher up in the trophy level we also cover species below. (G)
- CBD speaks a lot about adaptive potential and their ability to deliver ecosystem services so should we focus and monitor species with clear ecosystem services? (G)
- Is genetic diversity in itself considered an ecosystem service?
- We should focus on species that support resilience in ecosystems. (G)
- When selecting species lets pick species where we can actually follow up with management actions so that we can evaluate the effects of management.
- What do we do with domesticated species? They have very different N_e . (G)
- The species we select for proxy calculations should be representatives and we need to pick species for which we have data.

- We (SEPA) will not get extra funding so we need to select species that we can monitor for the long run so we need to be realistic and pragmatic.
 - Should we synchronise species lists with other countries? (G)
 - Who is responsible for monitoring species that are common in Europe but not Sweden? (G)
 - Economically important species should be included in the list.
3. We need to define what the purpose for monitoring genetic indicators is: Just to send a report to the CBD (then use the species that are easy to report on) or to actually monitor what happens over time with genetic diversity in Sweden - then we need to choose species that we can work with over a long time period and that are representative.
 4. CBD aims to get an overview of how the planet is doing. We want to monitor how Sweden is doing. Can affect the species to choose.
 5. The CBDs goal is 2030 - but the genetic indicators will not tell us much in such a short time. The purpose of the indicators is two fold; What is happening - are we moving towards a better state? What do the indicators tell us we need to do?
 6. There is no political will. We have the methods and the skills and people who want to do the work but the politicians are not saying “go” or funding this work long term.

Data is collected, structured and stored and the indicators are calculated

1. There is currently no general database for DNA based data. SwAM is developing one that will store data generated from work that they are responsible for and SEPA will join in on this database.
2. We need two types of databases: one for the raw data and one for the indicators.
3. Methods are different for creating a database for DNA based data and for proxy based data.
4. For proxy data we already have the red list database.
5. There is no way of calculating N_e for polyploid plants although they consist of 60% of all plants. (G)
6. Census data is very uncertain in Sweden and we lack it for large areas, many species and populations.
7. Time consuming to find data that is stored in personal computers and small databases. We also risk losing the data forever. (G)
8. No long-term structure in place for who does the calculations of the genetic indicators. It is based on project funding and is decided from case to case (DNA based). (G)
9. Reporting into a database is a new thing - there is a lot of old data spread around at universities etc.

10. The biobanks are not secure and the current ones are full but it has been an invaluable resource in calculating genetic indicators! International biobanks would be useful. (G)
11. What do we do with “left over” materials?
12. Challenge to synchronise other processes like for example the Habitats directive. The people doing the evaluations and collecting data are at large the same people/institutions but at the agencies they different people/departments have the responsibility. (G)
13. Using data from other reports to calculate genetic indicators. (G)
14. How can we consolidate for example the KOBO, BON IN A BOX and the red-list database?
15. How do we ensure long term stability for collecting data, storing data etc. (G)
16. There is a standard for how to evaluate “Nature worth” (Naturvärdesinventering) but it is costly
17. Is it possible to harmonize for HELCOM? (G)
18. Data needs to be searchable; from biobanks, herbaria and and other physical collections.(G)
19. Defining population is hard for several species. (G)
20. What happens if suddenly $N_e > 500$ is not considered the correct threshold? (G)

The report to the CBD is written and submitted

1. SEPA has been given the responsibility to oversee the work but there is not one person responsible for coordinating the whole process with selecting species etc. (G)
2. The main challenge from SEPAS side is time, financial resources and data. (G)
3. HaV will provide their indicator assessments to SEPA to be included in the national reporting.
4. Who does what and who manages the whole process from SEPA? (G)
5. How do we ensure long term stability for collecting data, storing data etc.?

Other challenges discussed - moving broader from the workflow

1. How can we make the results easily accessible and interesting for a large audience? It is relevant to communicate this widely and to show the status of Swedish nature.
2. How do we use the results from the reporting and monitoring in management?
3. How do we secure the tissue collected and used in monitoring with DNA techniques? With the rapid technical developments tissue is often more relevant to store than sequence data, but the collections are not secured but rely largely on individual researchers/projects.
4. How do we involve the stakeholders who were not present today (such as land owners, forestries, hunters etc) to inspire them and to make them see the point of genetic indicators and manage the resource in accordance with it?

Next steps

The GINAMO work packages will assess all challenges selected by the five countries as potentially benefiting from collaboration between GINAMO and the country stakeholders. The GINAMO work package members will assess if and how these can be incorporated into their work, and how the country stakeholders might be able to contribute. The result of this will then be reported back to the country workshop participants, together with potential next steps.

Reference materials

- Sweden has committed to the CBD Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework and must report to the CBD using novel genetic indicators for the first time, among a large range of indicators, first in February 2026, and then periodically, typically every three to four years. Critical steps are the selection of species to report on, collecting and interpreting available data on them for the calculation of indicators, and using a reproducible approach to building successive reports. Guidelines for these steps are available:
 - CBD guidelines:
<https://www.cbd.int/doc/c/92cf/b458/18519b4c0b487bf9bfc23988/sbstta-26-inf-14-en.pdf>
 - Guidelines from the Coalition of Conservation Genetics:
<https://ccgenetics.github.io/guidelines-genetic-diversity-indicators/>
 - <https://doi.org/10.17161/bi.v18i.22332>
- Genetic diversity must be protected because it allows for the long-term persistence, resilience and adaptive potential of species.
 - policy brief: <https://g-bikegenetics.eu/en/multimedia-policy-briefs-pubs/policy-briefs>
- The genetic indicators are pragmatic and can be computed using DNA data or non-DNA proxy data.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae006>
 - <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10592-024-01632-8>
- These indicators have been tested and validated for use in 9 countries, including Sweden.
 - <https://doi.org/10.32942/X2WK6T>
- National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) can be improved to include the protection of genetic diversity.
 - <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/biae106>
- Havs- och vattenmyndigheten (SWAM) web page about monitoring of genetic diversity:
<https://www.havochvatten.se/overvakning-och-uppfoljning/miljoovervakning/overvakning-av-genetisk-mangfald.html>
- Naturvårdsverket (SEPA) report on monitoring of genetic diversity:

<https://www.naturvardsverket.se/publikationer/6900/mapping-and-monitoring-genetic-diversity-in-sweden-a-proposal-for-species-methods-and-costs/>

- Naturvårdsverket (SEPA) report on monitoring of genetic diversity in pollinators:
<https://www.naturvardsverket.se/publikationer/6900/mapping-and-monitoring-genetic-diversity-in-sweden-suggestions-for-pollinating-species/>
- Monitoring genetic diversity with new indicators applied to an alpine freshwater top predator:
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/mec.16710>
- New indicators for monitoring genetic diversity applied to alpine brown trout populations using whole genome sequence data:
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/mec.17213>
- Range-wide and temporal genomic analyses reveal the consequences of near-extinction in Swedish moose:
<https://www.nature.com/articles/s42003-023-05385-x>
- Monitoring genome-wide diversity over contemporary time with new indicators applied to Arctic charr population:
<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10592-023-01586-3>
- Genetic Monitoring of Brown Trout Released Into a Novel Environment: Establishment and Genetic Impact on Natural Populations:
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1111/eva.70084>
- Practical application of indicators for genetic diversity in CBD post-2020 global biodiversity framework implementation:
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1470160X22006392>
- Genetic structure and diversity of the seagrass *Zostera marina* along a steep environmental gradient, with implications for genetic monitoring:
<https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/climate/articles/10.3389/fclim.2023.1303337/full>

APPENDIX I: Workshop Agenda

09.00	Välkomna, introduktion, utvärdering	11.30	LUNCH
09.40	Presentation: <u>GINAMO</u> och de genetiska indikatorerna	12.30	NS/U: Artslista - forts
	Presentation: Sveriges och CBD	15:15	NS/U: Att samla data, beräkna och förvara information
10.10	Paus	14:15	NS/U: rapportering till CBD
10.20	Processen för denna Workshop/ Flöde för rapportering	15.00	Paus
10.35	<u>Presentationsrunda/ Organisations</u> överblick	15:15	Sortera utmaningar
11.00	Nuvarande situation/utmaningar (NS/U): Artslista	16.15	Nästa steg, avslut och utvärdering
		17.00	SLUT

Photo: GINAMO

APPENDIX II: IUCN SSC CPSG

Our **mission**: to save threatened species by increasing the effectiveness of conservation efforts worldwide

Our **mantra**: every species that needs a plan is covered by an effective and implemented plan

For over 40 years we've accomplished this by:

- Providing culturally sensitive and respectful facilitation for stakeholder-inclusive conservation action planning.
- Developing and sharing innovative, interdisciplinary science-based tools and methods.
- Building capacity for species conservation planning worldwide.